

List of Primary Studies

Citation	Bibliographic Reference
Joembunthanaphong & Sriharee (2022)	Joembunthanaphong, P.; Sriharee, G. <i>The Improvement Process for the Software Development and Requirements Management to Achieve Capability Level 3 of CMMI</i> . In: ICSEC, 2022.
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